

DEVELOPMENT OF A STRUCTURE RELEVANT SPECIMEN FOR DAMAGE TOLERANCE STUDIES

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ABSTRACT

A preliminary investigation is reported of the development of a Structure Relevant specimen, less expensive than a full scale panel, but maintaining the essential design features of the panel configuration, for damage growth studies. Several SR-specimens were fabricated, damage was present in the form of artificial delaminations, compression loads were applied, C-scan damage areas and internal damage configurations were determined.

The failure mode of the SR-specimens consists of three phases: stable delamination buckling with increasing amplitude, followed by rapid delamination growth causing load redistribution, and finally slow delamination growth until total failure occurs at a gross strain level of 0.0061. Preferred delamination growth was discovered at interfaces adjacent to 90-degree layers, as expected.

Keywords: Damage Tolerance, Delamination Growth, Compression After Impact.

1. INTRODUCTION

The development of structural concepts for compression loaded, damage tolerant, stiffened composite panels, and the investigation of the failure mechanisms of these concepts, generally require the fabrication and testing of full scale stiffened panels, which is an expensive procedure. In this study a preliminary investigation is reported of an effort to develop a Structure Relevant (SR-) specimen, which is less expensive than a full scale panel, but maintains the essential design features of the panel configuration under investigation.

Damage tolerant designs are often based on multi-load path concepts, allowing controlled load redistribution, combined with features to delay damage growth, thereby achieving high failure strains. The investigation was focused on the question whether similar damage growth processes can be achieved with the relatively simple SR-specimens proposed. If so, the SR-specimens can be used to study the failure mechanisms of the related panel design concept, so that the effect of local design features on damage propagation can be evaluated to a larger extent, enabling the designer to optimize a panel design for damage tolerance.

The damage tolerant design concept for heavily loaded wing panels on which this study is based was developed by Boeing, and is reported in Reference 1. Figure 1 shows the features of this concept, with soft skin, doublers and discrete stiffeners. The configuration of the SR-specimen, derived from this concept, is a rectangular panel with similar geometry, representing a short section, consisting of one stiffener zone with adjacent skin. The stiffener itself is absent, but its influence on the behavior of the specimen is simulated by the support provided by an anti-buckling guide, as shown in Figure 2.

Three identical specimens were fabricated, each specimen containing identical "damage" in the form of two artificial delaminations: two circular bronze foils located above each other, but separated by a number of fiber-reinforced plies. The specimens were loaded in compression up to different load levels, one up to total failure, before they were dissected for fractography. Damage growth was monitored during the compression tests with strain, displacement, and acoustic emission recordings. C-scan damage areas were obtained after the compression test, before dissection.

2. DAMAGE GROWTH PROCESS

The failure behavior of the damage tolerant, stiffened panel concept under consideration, with impact damage present, under increasing compression loading, may be characterized by three phases: no damage growth at first, damage (delamination) growth after a certain load level is reached, until finally a critical damage configuration is formed and total failure occurs.

Impact damage in a stiffened panel consists of a complex combination of intralaminar cracks, fiber fractures, delaminations, etc. However, degradation of the strength of a panel under increased compressive loading might be dominated by a more tangible process: the propagation in the lateral panel direction of certain apparently "preferred" delaminations, resulting in the destabilization of wider zones of the specimen. The reduced stability of the specimen is caused by load eccentricities due to buckling of the delaminated sublaminates, and may lead to a final transverse shear failure mode of the remaining part of the cross section.

Delaminations caused by impact are generally stacked on top of each other. They are usually located at the interfaces between layers with different orientation. The size of the delaminations tends to increase, as seen in the impact direction, the larger ones located at the back side of the laminate. The shape of the delaminations is often oval or elliptic. The major axis of the ellipses tends to incline in the direction of the fibers of the "underlying" layer, again, as seen in the impact direction. Hence, the widest delaminations are expected at interfaces adjacent to and in front of the 90-degree layers. Of all the delaminations resulting from the impact, the widest ones may be the ones that actually grow under load. Support for this hypothesis is given in Figure 3, which shows part of the cross section of a stiffened panel that was impacted and loaded in compression up to failure. The photograph was taken at a short distance from the fracture line. The stiffener separated and is not shown, but this separation was probably a secondary effect. It is possible that the delamination growth and buckling of the two sublaminates in the skin did induce final failure. It is apparent from the photograph that both delaminations run along an interface in front of the 90-degree layers (white lines in the photograph). It is also interesting to note that the delamination at the bottom crosses several layers between the edge of a short 90-degree layer and the continuous 90-degree layer below.

In the study reported here, the performance of the SR-specimen with respect to damage growth under load was evaluated in particular by investigating whether the propagation of certain preferred delaminations actually takes place.

3. SPECIMENS

Three identical specimens, labelled BE-A.1, BE-A.2, and BE-A.3 were used to study damage growth, starting at two circular artificial delaminations. The geometry and instrumentation are shown in Figure 4. The axial stiffness distribution of the SR-specimens is shown in Figure 5, and the laminate composition is shown in Figure 6. The specimens contained quasi-isotropic skin laminates. The interleaved doublers consist of 7 stacks of 4 to 6 layers, almost all of which are 0-degree layers. The design load of a panel with cross sections in this range is in the order of 4.0 - 4.5 kN/mm. The ratio of the axial stiffness of the low-stiffness zones and the high stiffness zones is 0.59.

4. LOCATION OF ARTIFICIAL DELAMINATIONS

The impact site, estimated as the most critical for the residual strength of the stiffened panel configuration considered, is located right under the stiffness transition zone. The three specimens were each provided with two artificial delaminations, consisting of circular bronze foils (30 μm thick with 60 mm diameter), located above each other, but separated by a number of plies. The location of the center of the foils coincided with the impact location considered most critical. The location of the foils in the laminate stacking sequence is illustrated in Figure 6. For ease of fabrication it was not contemplated to position the foils adjacent to a 90-degree layer, where delaminations are expected to be most critical. Instead, two interfaces between continuous sublaminates and doubler sublaminates were selected, near the flat side of the panel where local buckling of sublaminates was expected. As the three specimens were intended to be used for the study of damage propagation, it was deemed essential that the initial damage condition of the specimens, each to be loaded up to different levels, was the same. For that reason artificial delaminations were preferred as initial "damage" above damage that is introduced by impact.

5. TEST FIXTURE

The SR-specimens were mounted in an anti-buckling guide during the compression test. The specimen support fixture is shown in Figure 2. It consists of a front plate with access hole for instrumentation and visual inspection, and a solid back plate. The specimen is supported by two rows of swiveling disks at the longitudinal sides, mounted in the front and back plate, representing nearly simple support conditions. At the back, the specimen is supported by a single row of swiveling disks along the center line, simulating the stiffener support.

6. EXPERIMENTS

The three specimens were loaded in compression to different levels to study damage growth. Specimen BE-A.1 was loaded up to failure, after which the internal damage was studied by fractography, a short distance away from the fracture line. The other two specimens were loaded up to lower levels, and the tests were stopped before total failure took place, so that damage growth could be observed by fractography at cross sections through the center line of the panels.

The response of the specimens was recorded with several strain gauges and displacement transducers, positioned at the flat and visible side of the specimens, as shown in Figure 4a. Two strain gauges, labelled sg2 and sg3, were located at the surface above the artificial delaminations, sg2 measuring longitudinal strain and sg3 measuring lateral strain. Strain gauge sg1 was located at the center line of the specimen, far away from the delaminated area, but on the load path of which the delaminated area was a part, so that it recorded load redistribution due to damage growth. Two displacement transducers measured the end-shortening of the specimen, and the average value recorded by these transducers was divided by the specimen length and is presented as "gross strain" in subsequent figures. Two displacement transducers, labelled LVDT-1 and LVDT-2 measured transverse displacements, LVDT-2 at the delaminated area, and LVDT-1 at the center of the specimen, at a location where the delamination was expected to develop after it propagated. Acoustic emission was also recorded, but not in a very sophisticated manner. Hence, acoustic data emissions are discussed in a qualitative way.

6.1. Compression tests

Specimen BE-A.1 was loaded up to failure without intermissions. The (lateral) fracture line passed through the center of the artificial delaminations. Load versus strain behavior is shown in Figure 7-a, which includes the gross strain defined above, and a line representing the gross strain after the curve was shifted to the origin. Load versus transverse displacement is shown in Figure 7b. Figure 7b also shows a qualitative image of the acoustic emission recorded during the test.

At a gross strain level of 0.0029 (240 kN) a sublaminar buckled out, as indicated by the strain and displacement recordings obtained at this position, shown in Figures 7a-b. At a gross strain level of 0.0052 (420 kN) the buckled, delaminated sublaminar suddenly propagated into the doubler area, as indicated by LVDT-1. This propagation took place in three phases according to LVDT-1, rapidly at first, then somewhat slower and then rapidly again, until suddenly the load dropped at a gross strain of 0.0055 (445 kN). This load drop was caused by a global stiffness loss of the specimen, as is indicated by the gross strain curve. At this point, strain gauge sg1 indicated for the first (and only) time that a noticeable load redistribution took place, as the strain straight above the damaged area had decreased. After this phenomenon occurred, a transition into an apparently stable damage configuration had taken place, as the load could be increased further without any damage growth recorded by the data channels, until total failure occurred at 497 kN, at a theoretical gross strain of 0.0061 (the shifted gross strain line ignores the sudden stiffness loss of the specimen, which otherwise would have indicated a failure strain of 0.0066).

The acoustic emission recording is shown in a qualitative way in Figure 7b. At the onset of local buckling the activity, represented by the magnitude of the peaks that were recorded, was raised to a slightly higher level, which remained constant at first, then increased linearly as the amplitude of the buckled delamination increased. As soon as the buckled delamination started to grow and propagate rapidly into the doubler area, the activity did not increase any longer, but remained almost constant up to failure, even showing a slight dip.

Specimen BE-A.2 was loaded up to 450 kN, or a gross strain of 0.0053, after which the specimen was unloaded. The strains, transverse displacements and acoustic emission data were all very similar to the data obtained for specimen BE-A.1, except that the sudden delamination growth had not yet taken place according to LVDT-1 (it took place at 0.0052 and 420 kN for specimen BE-A.1). As will be discussed later, the C-scan damage area had grown only slightly.

Specimen BE-A.3 was first loaded up to 350 kN, and repeated the behavior of the other two specimens, including the buckling of the delaminated sublaminates. Afterwards, no C-scan damage area growth was detected. Subsequently, specimen BE-A.3 was loaded again, this time up to 460 kN, or a gross strain level of 0.0059, when a bang was heard and the test was stopped. The strain, displacement, and acoustic emission recordings were again very similar to the values obtained for specimen BE-A.1, shown in Figures 7a-b. The onset of local buckling had advanced somewhat (occurring at a gross strain of 0.0025, at 210 kN), but rapid delamination growth occurred again at a gross strain level of 0.0052 (424 kN). The loud bang at 0.0059 was accompanied by a load drop due to a loss of global stiffness. The corresponding strain decrease at strain gauge sg1 confirmed the occurrence of a significant load redistribution. The jump into a new damage configuration had taken place a little later than the corresponding behavior of specimen BE-A.1 (at 0.0059 and 460 kN versus 0.0055 and 445 kN for specimen BE-A.1), while the out-of-plane deflection recorded by LVDT-1 at this point made a bigger jump, to the same value of 2.2 mm, however. It could not be investigated whether the newly developed damage configuration was as stable as that of specimen BE-A.1 at this point, as the specimen had to survive for a more detailed study of the damage by fractography.

6.2. C-scan damage area

After the compression tests, C-scan damage areas were established for specimens BE-A.2 and BE-A.3. As shown in Figure 8a, the damage area of specimen BE-A.2 had hardly grown. This confirms the conclusions of the analysis of the test data, which revealed that this specimen had merely experienced delamination buckling with increasing amplitude, but without significant delamination growth. The C-scan damage area obtained for specimen BE-A.3 is shown in Figure 8b. This illustration shows that the damage in this specimen had grown across the doubler area, even extending into the base skin at both sides. According to the analysis of the test data of specimens BE-A.1 and BE-A.3, the damage configuration shown in Figure 8b corresponds to a more stable state, which occurred after a significant redistribution of load. From Figure 8b it is tentatively concluded that this load redistribution occurred when the delamination of the buckled sublaminates abruptly propagated across the full width of the doubler area. Apparently, the buckled sublaminates had suddenly become so large that it was able to shed a substantial part of its load. From this point in the damage configuration development, further delamination growth is confined to the base skin areas on both sides of the doubler, as experienced by specimen BE-A.1. Delamination growth in these low stiffness areas hardly reduces the specimen stiffness any further, and was therefore not recorded by the instruments, giving the impression of a quasi-stabilized damage configuration.

6.3. Internal damage description

After conducting the compression tests and obtaining the C-scan damage areas, the specimens were cut and polished, so the internal damage could be observed by microscope. A summary of the findings is described in Figures 9a-c, where delaminations are shown in schematic form.

Figure 9a shows the internal damage of specimen BE-A.2, which was loaded until the delaminated sublaminates buckled out with increasing amplitude, but before any propagation of the delamination was detected by the test instruments, which is confirmed by the C-scan damage area shown in Figure 8a. Figure 9a indicates that the artificial delaminations were not located at the most "natural" interfaces, because the compressive loading caused the delaminations to jump to the back side of the nearest 90-degree plies.

Figure 9b shows the internal damage of specimen BE-A.3, which was loaded until the delaminated sublaminates propagated across the entire doubler. Comparing this figure with Figure 9a shows that the first part of the damage growth was identical to that of specimen BE-A.2, with delaminations jumping to the nearest 90-degree plies, easily crossing the 0-degree plies, and growing along the back sides of the 90-degree plies. With further growth, a tendency to make the much harder crossover to the front side of the 90-degree plies is noticed at the doubler region of the specimens, farther away from the original artificial delaminations.

Figure 9c shows the internal damage of specimen BE-A.1, which had been loaded up to total failure. In this case the internal damage is shown for a cross section 30 mm away from the center of the artificial delaminations, to avoid the chaos at the fracture line which ran right through the center of the artificial delaminations. The damage pattern obtained for the other two specimens can be recognized in the damage pattern of specimen BE-A.1, except that the initial delaminations extend along the front of the 90-degree plies. Additional delaminations in the

upper half of the specimen are probably induced during the final catastrophic failure of the specimen. Final failure of the specimen most likely occurred when the delaminations in the base skin reached the edges of the specimen, possibly jumping from an elliptic to a rectangular shape, similar to what happened when the delamination crossed the doubler. The shock of the sudden delamination growth, and the subsequent load redistribution were probably sufficient to cause the specimen, already loaded to a high strain level of 0.0061, to fail in transverse shear due to the load eccentricity.

From these observations it is concluded that the interfaces at the front side of the 90-degree layers, already the obvious locations for the widest delaminations resulting from impacts, are also the most likely locations for delaminations to grow under compressive loading of the specimen. The presence of the artificial delaminations apparently did initiate delamination propagation along the "wrong" side of the 90-degree plies, plies which are hard to cross for delaminations growing in the lateral direction.

7. MODEL

In the previous chapters the failure mechanism for a particular damage tolerant stiffened panel concept was described. The complete sequence of initial damage, rapid damage (delamination) growth, load redistribution stabilizing the structure, and final failure mode, representative for the behavior of a damage tolerant, multi-load path structure, was observed and described. The study was not meant to be complete: the specimens were built up according to one particular lay-up scheme, and only one damage configuration was included. Hence, it can not be concluded that the specimen, with the lay-up scheme and the initial damage configuration as selected, represents the worst case scenario for this damage tolerant design concept. However, the specimen configuration is a successful one, only to be improved with the knowledge gained in this study, and the damage configuration seems severe, with the major delaminations located at the flat, unsupported side of the panel. Therefore, it is considered worthwhile to model the specimen, including the quasi-stable damage configuration established in the final stage of its life, for the purpose of calculating the Compression After Impact strength of a stiffened panel, designed according to the concept under investigation. The model proposed for this calculation is shown in Figure 10.

8. CONCLUSIONS

A preliminary investigation is reported of the development of a Structure Relevant specimen, which maintains the essential features of a stiffened panel configuration, in order to study damage growth behavior at limited cost. Damage tolerant designs are based on multi-load path concepts, allowing controlled load redistribution, combined with features to delay damage growth, thereby achieving high failure strains. The investigation was focused on the question whether similar damage growth processes can be achieved with the relatively simple SR-specimens proposed. Damage growth was evaluated in particular with respect to the question whether the tendency of delaminations to grow along certain preferred interfaces, as observed with full scale stiffened panels, is also present in the SR-specimen.

The failure mode of the SR-specimens consisted of three phases: a first phase of stable delamination buckling with increasing amplitude, a second phase of rapid delamination growth, until the delamination jumped across the doubler area, causing a significant load redistribution, and a final phase with slow delamination growth in the base skin zones at the edges, until total failure occurred at the high gross strain of 0.0061. Preferred delamination growth was discovered at the interfaces adjacent to the 90-degree layers, as expected.

The SR-specimen proposed has the characteristics of a full scale stiffened panel, and can be used for damage tolerance studies, aiming for the optimization of cross sections and laminate stacking sequences, and for the development of models for the calculation of the strength after impact of a stiffened panel in the design phase.

9. REFERENCE

1. McCarthy, J.E., Roeseler, W.G., "Durability and Damage Tolerance of Large Composite Primary Aircraft Structure (LCPAS)", NASA CR-3767, 1984.

Fig. 1 Damage tolerant multi-load path stiffened panel concept with soft skin, discrete stiffeners and doublers (Ref. 1)

Fig. 2 Structure relevant specimen with anti-buckling support

Fig. 3 Cross section of a failed panel with detached stiffener

Fig. 4 SR-specimen geometry and instrumentation

Fig. 5 Laminate properties

Fig. 6 Location of the artificial delaminations in the stacking sequence

a) Load versus strain

Fig. 7 Compression test results for specimen BE-A.1

b) Load versus transverse displacement

a) C-scan damage area BE-A.2 after delamination buckling

b) C-scan damage area BE-A.3 after delamination growth

Fig. 8 C-scan damage area's of specimens BE-A.2 and BE-A.3

a) Internal damage at the center line across the artificial delaminations after delamination buckling (BE-A.2)

b) Internal damage at the center line across the artificial delaminations after delamination growth (BE-A.3)

c) Internal damage at a cross section 30 mm above the artificial delaminations after total failure (BE-A.1)

Fig. 9 Internal damage of specimens BE-A.1, BE-A.2 and BE-A.3

a) Location of delaminations in the cross section

b) Location of the delaminations on the specimen planform

Fig. 10 Model of specimen with assumed delaminations for compression after impact strength